

Girth Inequality In Planar Graphs

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Abstract

As defined in graph theory, the girth of a given graph is the length of its shortest cycle. Most of the papers, that mentioned the girth of a graph, I will mention here [1, 2, 3 and 4], investigated other features when the girth was one of the data, or described algorithms to find the girth when the graph is given. The purpose of this paper is to give inequalities, which explain girth's relationship with the number of edges, the number of vertices and the number of faces, in a planar and connected graph.

Introduction

Definition 1: A connected graph is a graph such that for each pair of vertices x and y there exists a path (or walk) beginning at x and ending at y . When a path of length s is a sequence of vertices:

$x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_s$, such that for all $i > 1$, x_i is adjacent to x_{i+1} .

When in a path the first vertex and the last vertex come together, then we call it a circle in the graph.

Definition 2: A bonding element of a graph is a concatenation maximum subgraph, which is, its vertex group set, V , have a path between each of its two vertices, and all the neighbors, of every vertex from V , are included also in V .

The number of all the bonding elements in the graph, we will mark with θ .

Definition 3: An edge in a connected given graph G (i.e., with a number of bonding elements equal to 1), is called a bridge in G , if with its removal we get two bonding elements.

Example 1:

It is clear that the edge e in the graph of Figure 1 is a bridge.

Figure 1

Example 2:

It is clear that, there is no edge that is; a bridge in the graph of Figure 2.

Figure 2

Definition 4: A planar graph is a graph that we can draw on the plane without cutting between its edges.

Definition 5: A face in a planar graph is a bounded area of connected vertices with edges that unambiguously describe the face, that is, the boundary of a face.

Each planar graph has an outer face, which is usually marked in F_∞ .

Denote by $F(G)$ the set of all faces of G , and $f = |F(G)|$.

Definition 6: The girth of a graph is the length of its shortest cycle.

If a graph has no cycles, we define its girth as ∞ .

Let $g(G)$ denote the girth of graph G .

Example 3:

$g(N_n) = \infty$, for all $n > 1$, when N_n denote the empty graph, n vertexes with no edges.

$g(k_n) = 3$, for all $n \geq 3$, when k_n the complete graph, n vertexes such that every pair of vertices is connected by an edge.

$g(K_{n,m}) = 4$, for all $n, m > 1$, when $k_{n,m}$ denote the bipartite graph, that is, a set of graph vertices decomposed into two disjoint sets, such that no two vertices within the same set are adjacent.

$g(Q_n) = 4$, for all $n > 2$, when Q_n denote n -dimensional cube, that is, a graph defined as follows: $V(Q_n) = \{a_1, a_2, a_3, \dots, a_n\} : 1 \leq i \leq n, a_i \in \{0, 1\}$, and two vertices are neighbors if and only if the dimensional vectors of their vertices are identical except for one lesson.

$g(T_n) = \infty$, for all $n \geq 3$, when T_n denote a connected graph with no cycles.

Let $G : (V, E)$ a planar and connected graph, and denote by n, m , to $|V|$ and $|E|$ respectively, let so f denote the number of all the faces of G , the Euler's formula states that:

$$n + f - m = 2.$$

New result:

Our main result presented in the following theorems:

Theorem 1:

Let G a planar and connected graph, if we denote by n, m and g to the number of vertexes, number of edges and the girth of G respectively, then the next inequality always holds,

$$\frac{2}{g} - \frac{2}{m} + \frac{n}{m} \geq 1$$

Example 4:

It is clear that the graph depicted in Figure 3 contains:

$n = 14, m = 15, f = 3$, and $g = 7$.

It is clear that there is

Figure 3

$$\frac{2}{g} - \frac{2}{m} + \frac{n}{m} = \frac{2}{7} - \frac{2}{15} + \frac{14}{15} = \frac{114}{105} \geq 1$$

Proof of Theorem 1:

Let G a planar graph, and let n, m, f and g be the number of vertexes, number of edges, number of the faces and the girth number, in G , respectively.

First, and without limiting the generality, we can assume that the graph is also connected.

Otherwise, consider the value of the expression $\frac{2}{g} - \frac{2}{m} + \frac{n}{m}$, in each bondage element of the graph G .

We can assume also that $n \geq g$ because if $n \leq g - 1$, then G is a graph without circles and

$$m \leq n - 1.$$

We will prove the Theorem by induction on n .

The basis of induction:

Since there are no cases in which $n \leq 2$, then we check the first case when, $n = 3$. In this case it will be: $n = 3$, $m = 3$, and $g = 3$. In addition, the graph is in a form of a triangle.

Look at Figure 4:

Figure 4

It is true that the inequality:

$$\frac{2}{g} - \frac{2}{m} + \frac{n}{m} = \frac{2}{3} - \frac{2}{3} + \frac{3}{3} = 1 \geq 1$$

Is hold.

Now, we assume that the inequality correctness for any number less than n , $n > 3$ and we will prove that it exists for n .

In order to complete the proof, we differentiate between two cases.

First case:

If G contains within it, a bridge ϑ i.e. an edge whose removal yields two bonding elements.

After removal of ϑ we will mark the two bonding elements with G_1 , and G_2 .

In addition, suppose that for $i = 1, 2$, in the binding component G_i there are n_i vertices and m_i edges.

From the assumption of the induction in G_1 hold:

$$\frac{2}{g} - \frac{2}{m_1} + \frac{n_1}{m_1} \geq 1$$

From the assumption of the induction in G_2 hold:

$$\frac{2}{g} - \frac{2}{m_2} + \frac{n_2}{m_2} \geq 1$$

Now, evaluate the phrase: $\frac{2}{g} - \frac{2}{m} + \frac{n}{m}$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{2}{g} - \frac{2}{m} + \frac{n}{m} &= \frac{2}{g} - \frac{2}{m_1 + m_2} + \frac{n_1}{m_1 + m_2} \\ &> \frac{2}{g} - \frac{2}{m_1} + \frac{n_1}{m_1 + m_2} \\ &= \frac{2}{g} - \frac{2}{m_1} + \frac{n_1}{m_1} + \frac{n_2}{m_2} \\ &\geq 1 + \frac{n_2}{m_2} > 1. \end{aligned}$$

(Note that $\frac{2}{m_1 + m_1} \leq \frac{2}{m_1}$, and $\frac{n_2}{m_2} > 0$).

In summary, we received: $\frac{2}{g} - \frac{2}{m} + \frac{n}{m} \geq 1$.

Second

case:

If there is no edge that is a bridge in G , (that is, any edge we remove from the graph will leave the graph connected), so every edge belongs to some circle, i.e. every edge separates between the scopes of exactly two faces.

will mark at t_j , the number of faces surrounded by j edges, so since each edge counted twice, once for each face in which it is a partner, hence: $f = \sum_j t_j$ and $\sum_j j \cdot t_j = 2m$.

Now, we find a condition on f face number:

$$\begin{aligned} g \cdot f &= g \cdot \sum_j t_j \\ &= \sum_j g \cdot t_j \\ &\leq \sum_{j>g} j \cdot t_j \end{aligned}$$

$$= \sum_j j \cdot t_j$$

$$= 2m$$

We received that $g \cdot f \leq 2m$, then $f \leq \frac{2m}{g}$.

In replacing $f \leq \frac{2m}{g}$ on the Euler formula $2 = n + f - m$, we will receive:

$$2 = n + f - m$$

$$2 \leq n + \frac{2m}{g} - m$$

$$\frac{2}{m} \leq \frac{n}{m} + \frac{2}{g} - 1$$

$$1 \leq \frac{n}{m} + \frac{2}{g} - \frac{2}{m}$$

This completes the proof of theorem 1.

Corollary:

In G a planar and a connected graph, if we denote by n , m , f and g to be the number of vertexes, the number of edges, the faces number and the girth number in G , respectively, then the following always holds:

$$(I) \quad f \leq \frac{2m}{g}$$

$$(II) \quad m \geq \frac{1}{2}fg$$

$$(III) \quad n \geq 2 + \left(1 - \frac{2}{g}\right)m$$

Proof of the Corollary:

We got (I) from the proof of the previous theorem; from (I), if we subtract m we get exactly (II).

To show (III), we will make up $2 - n + m = f$ from the Euler formula in (II):

$$m \geq \frac{1}{2}fg$$

$$m \geq \frac{1}{2}(2 - n + m)g$$

$$2m \geq 2g - ng + mg$$

$$ng \geq 2g + mg - 2m$$

$$n \geq 2 + m - \frac{2m}{g}$$

$$n \geq 2 + \left(1 - \frac{2}{g}\right)m$$

This completes the proof of the Corollary.

Example 5:

Figure 3 contains:

$n = 14$, $m = 15$, $f = 3$, and $g = 7$.

It is clear that according to Corollary 1, the following holds:

$$(I) \quad f \leq \frac{2m}{g}$$

$$3 \leq \frac{2 \cdot 15}{7}$$

$$(II) \quad m \geq \frac{1}{2}fg$$

$$15 \geq \frac{1}{2} \cdot 3 \cdot 7$$

$$(III) \quad n \geq 2 + \left(1 - \frac{2}{g}\right)m$$

$$14 \geq 2 + \left(1 - \frac{2}{7}\right)15$$

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